

Research Article**Applying Multiple Stochastic iterated integral to moment inequalities for Wiener Functional**

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Abstract

In several applications, as limit theorems, large deviations, degree of Wiener maps, calculation of the Radon- Nikodym, etc, we show that the log-sobolev inequality implies the exponential integrability of the square of the Wiener functional whose derivatives are essentially bounded. We shall examine with general measures which satisfy a logarithmic sobolev inequality and an interpolation inequality which state that the sobolev norm of the first order can be upper bounded by the product of the second order and of the zeroth order sobolev norms.

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Introduction

The application of Multiple Stochastic iterated integral to moment inequalities for Wiener Functional will involve two major result. The first result is concern with the tail probabilities of the wiener functional with essentially bounded Gross-Sobolev derivative, this result is a straight forward generalization of the celebrated fernique's lemma which state that the square of the supremum of Brownian path on any bounded interval has an exponential moment provided it is multiplied with a sufficiently small positive constant (Stock and Varagham, 1979).The second result state that for a wiener functional $F \in D_{p,1}$, we have

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$$E_w \times E_z [U(F(w) - F(z))] \leq E_w \times E_z \left[U \left(\frac{\pi}{2} I_1(\nabla F(w))(z) \right) \right], \quad (1.1)$$

Where w and z represent two independent Wiener's path, then E_w and E_z are the corresponding expectations $I_1(\nabla F(w))(z)$ is the first order Wiener integral with respect to z of $\nabla F(w)$ and U is any lower bounded, convex function on $\mathfrak{R}$.

We shall show in this work that the log-Sobolev inequality implies the exponential integrability of the square of the wiener functional (Ustunel, 2018) whose derivatives are essentially bounded. In general we shall examine measures satisfying a log-Sobolev inequality.

Preliminaries and Notations

Here we shall present some related concepts and notations that will enhance better understanding of the reader and other researchers.

Brownian motion and Wiener measures

Let $W = C_0([0, 1])$, defined W_t as to be the coordinate functional i.e for $w \in W$ and $t \in [0, 1]$. Let $W_t(w) = w(t)$, if we note $w(t)$ by $B_t = \delta\{W_t, s < t\}$ then the following theorem is well known (Ustunel, 2018).

Theorem 2.1

There is one and only one measure μ on W which satisfies the following properties

$$\mu\{w \in W : W_0(w) = 0\} = 1$$

For any $f \in C_b^\infty(\mathfrak{R})$, the stochastic process, process $(t, w) \rightarrow f(W_t(w)) - \frac{1}{2} \int_0^t \Delta f(W_s(w)) ds$ is a (B_t, μ) -Martingale, where Δ denotes Laplace operator. μ is called the (standard) Wiener measure.

From the above theorem, it follows that for $t > s$,

$$E_\mu [e^{i\alpha(W_t - W_s)} | B_s] = \exp \left\{ -\frac{1}{2} \alpha^2 (t - s) \right\}. \quad (2.1)$$

Hence $(t, w) \leftrightarrow W_t(w)$ is a continuous additive process with independent increment and $(W_t; t \in [0, 1])$ is also [3] a continuous Martingale.

Stochastic Integration

The stochastic integration with respect to the Brownian motion is first defined on the adapted step processes and then extended to their completion by isometry. A mapping $k: [0, 1] \times W \rightarrow \mathfrak{R}$ is called a step process if it can be represented in the following form;

$$k_t(w) = \sum_{i=1}^n a_i(w) \cdot I_{\{t_i, (t_{i+1})(t)\}} \cdot a_i(w) \in L^2(B_{t_i}) \quad (2.2)$$

For such a step process, we define its stochastic integral with respect to the Brownian motion which (Deereusefond and Ustunel, 1998) is denoted by

$$I(k) = \int_0^1 k_s dW_s(w) \quad (2.3)$$

As to be

$$\sum_{i=1}^n a_i(w) (W_{t_{i+1}}(w) - W_{t_i}(w)) \quad (2.4)$$

Using the independence of the increment of $(W_t, t \in [0, 1])$, it is obvious that

$$E \left[\left| \int_0^1 k_s dW_s \right|^2 \right] = E \int_0^1 |k_s|^2 ds \quad (2.5)$$

i.e I is an isometry from the adapted step processes into $L^2(\mu)$, hence it has a unique extension as an isometry from

$L^2([0, 1] \times W, \mathcal{A}, dt \times d\mu) \xrightarrow{I} L^2(\mu)$ where $\mathcal{A}$ is the sigma algebra on $[0, 1] \times W$ generated by the adapted, left (or right) continuous processes. The extension of $I(k)$ is called the stochastic integral of k and it is represented as $\int_0^t k_s dW_s$. If we define

$I_t(k) = \int_0^t k_s dW_s$ as $\int_0^1 I_{[0, 1]}(s) k_s dW_s$ it follows from Doob inequality that the stochastic process $t \leftrightarrow I_t(k)$ is a continuous square integrable Martingale.

I can be extended to any adapted process k with some localization (Hajek and Wong, 1981; Deereusefond *et al.*, 1993) methods such that

$$\int_0^1 k_s^2(w) ds < \infty \quad (2.6)$$

In the case of (2.6), the process $t \leftrightarrow I_t(k)$ become a local Martingale, there exist a sequence of stopping times increasing to one, say $(T_n, n \in \mathcal{N})$ implies that $t \mapsto I_{t \wedge T_n}(k)$ is a square integrable Martingale.

A stochastic process $(X_t, t \geq 0)$ with values in a finite dimensional Euclidean space is called an Ito process if it can be represented as

$$X_t = X_0 + \int_0^t a_s dW_s + \int_0^t b_s ds \quad (2.7)$$

Where $(W_t, t \geq 0)$ is a vector valued Brownian motion and a and b are respectively matrix and vector valued, adapted measurable process with

$$\int_0^t (|a_s|^2 + |b_s|) ds < \infty \quad (2.8)$$

almost surely for any $t \geq 0$

Ito Formula

The following result is one of the most important application of the stochastic integration.

Theorem 2.2

Let $f \in L^2(\mathfrak{R})$ and let $(X_t, t \in [0, 1])$ be an Ito process such that

$$X_t = X_0 + \int_0^t k_r dW_r + \int_0^t \mu_r dr \quad (2.9)$$

Where X_0 is B_0 - measurable, k and μ are adapted process with

$$\int_0^t [|k_r|^2 + |\mu_r|] dr \leq \infty \quad (2.10)$$

almost surely

Then

$$f(X_t) = f(X_0) + \int_0^t f'(X_s) k_s dW_s + \frac{1}{2} \int_0^t f''(X_s) k_s^2 ds + \int_0^t f'(X_r) \mu_r dr \quad (2.11)$$

Remark 2.1: this formula is also valid in the several dimensional case. In fact if k and μ are adapted processes with values in $\mathbb{R}^n \otimes \mathbb{R}^m$ and $\mathbb{R}^m$ respectively whose components are satisfying the condition in theorem 2.2, then we have for any $f \in L^2(\mathbb{R}^m)$,

$$f(X_t) = f(X_0) + \int_0^t \partial_i f(X_r) k_{ij}(r) dW_r^j + \int_0^t \partial_i f(X_r) \mu_i(r) dr + \frac{1}{2} \int_0^t \partial_{ij}^2 f(X_r) (k_r k_r^*)_{ij} dr \quad (2.12)$$

almost surely.

To prove this, we shall proceed by examining the following lemma

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Lemma 2.1

Let $X = (X_t, t \geq 0)$ and $Y = (Y_t, t \geq 0)$ be two Ito real-valued processes, then

$$X_t Y_t = X_0 Y_0 + \int_0^t X_s dY_s + \int_0^t Y_s dX_s + [X, Y]_t \quad (2.13)$$

almost surely, where $[X, Y]$ denotes the Doob- Meyer process. In particular,

$$X_t^2 = X_0^2 + 2 \int_0^t X_s dx_s + [X, X]_t \quad (2.14)$$

Proof:

Obviously it is easy to prove the relation (2.14) since we can obtain (2.13) via a polarization argument. Since X has almost surely continuous trajectories, using a stopping time argument we can assume that X is (Usunel and Zakai, 1992) almost surely bounded. Assume now that $\{t_1, \dots, t_n\}$ is a partition of (Kallenberg 1991), (Usunel and Zakai, 1989) $[0, t]$ and it is denoted by $(\mathcal{M}_t, t \geq 0)$, the local Martingale part and $(\mathcal{A}_t, t \geq 0)$, the finite variation part of X . We have

$$X_t^2 - X_0^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n (X_{t_i} - X_{t_{i-1}})^2 + 2 \sum_{i=1}^n X_{t_{i-1}} (X_{t_i} - X_{t_{i-1}}) \quad (2.15)$$

$$= \sum_{i=1}^n (X_{t_i}^2 - X_{t_{i-1}}^2) + 2 \sum_{i=1}^n X_{t_{i-1}} (\mathcal{M}_{t_i} - \mathcal{M}_{t_{i-1}}) + 2 \sum_{i=1}^n X_{t_{i-1}} (\mathcal{A}_{t_i} - \mathcal{A}_{t_{i-1}}) \quad (2.16)$$

Now when $\sup_i |t_i - t_{i-1}| \rightarrow 0$, then the first term at the right hand side of (2.16)

converges to $[X, X]_t$ and the sum of the second term converges to $2 \int_0^t X_s dX_s$ in probability.

Proof of the Ito formula:

Using a stopping argument, we can assume that X takes its values in a bounded interval, say $[-i, i]$. The interest of this argument resides in the fact that we can approach a L^2 function, as well as its first two derivatives uniformly by polynomials on any compact interval (Hung and Cambanis, 1978). On the other hand, using lemma 2.1, it become very glaring that the formula is valid for the polynomials.

Let $(\Gamma f)_t$ be the random variable

$$f(X_t) - f(X_0) - \int_0^t f'(X_s) dX_s - \frac{1}{2} \int_0^t f''(X_s) d[X, X]_s$$

Assume moreover that $(p_n, n \geq 1)$ is a sequence of polynomials such that $(p_n, n \geq 1)$, $(p'_n, n \geq 1)$, $(p''_n, n \geq 1)$ converges uniformly on $[-i, i]$ to f' and to f'' respectively. Choosing a subsequence, if necessary we may assume that $\sup_{x \in [-i, i]} (|f(x) - p_n(x)| +$

$|f''(x) - p''_n(x)|) \leq \frac{1}{n}$, applying Doob and Chebychev inequalities, it is obvious that

$(\Gamma f)_t - (\Gamma p_n)_t$ converges to zero in probability, since $(\Gamma p_n)_t = 0$ a.s, $(\Gamma f)_t$ should be zero also a.s and this complete the proof of the Ito formula.

Proof :

To prove this, we have to prove Leibniz formulae whose prove follows its finite dimensional version. Suppose that $p > q$ and let $\varphi \in D$, using the identity $\delta^p f = I_p(f)$ and the fact that δ^p is the adjoint of the operator, we get from lemma 3.2

$$\begin{aligned} E[I_p(f)I_q(g)\phi] &= E\left[\left((f, \nabla^p(I_q(g) \widehat{\otimes} \nabla^{p-i} \phi)_{H \otimes p})\right)\right] \\ &= E\left[\sum_{i=0}^p C_{p,i} \left((f, \nabla^p(I_q(g) \widehat{\otimes} \nabla^{p-i} \phi)_{H \otimes p})\right)\right] \\ &= E\left[\sum_{i=0}^p C_{p,i} \frac{q^i}{(q-i)!} \left((f, \nabla^p(I_{q-i}(g) \widehat{\otimes} \nabla^{p-i} \phi)_{H \otimes p})\right)\right] \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^p C_{p,i} \frac{q^i}{(q-i)!} E\left[(f, I_{q-i}(g) \otimes \nabla^{p-i} \phi)_{H \otimes p}\right] \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^p C_{p,i} \frac{q^i}{(q-i)!} E\left[(f, I_{q-i}(g) \otimes_i f, \nabla^{p-i} \phi)_{H \otimes (p-g)}\right] \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^p C_{p,i} \frac{q^i}{(q-i)!} E\left[(g) \otimes_i f, \nabla^{q-i} \nabla^{p-i} \phi)_{H \otimes (p+g-2i)}\right] \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^p C_{p,i} \frac{q^i}{(q-i)!} E\left[(g) \otimes_i f, \nabla^{p+q-2i} \phi)_{H \otimes (p+g-2i)}\right] \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^p C_{p,i} \frac{q^i}{(q-i)!} E\left[I_{p+q-2i}(g \widehat{\otimes}_i f), \phi\right] \end{aligned}$$

Where $C_{p,i} = \frac{p^i}{(p-i)!i!}$ and the proof of the lemma follows;

By the help of this lemma, we will prove;

Theorem 2.1

$I_p(f)$ and $I_q(g)$ are independent if and only if $f \otimes_1 g = 0$ a.s on $[0,1]^{p+q-2}$

Proof: ($\Rightarrow$): by independence, (Usunel and Zakai, 1989; Hung and Cambanis, 1978) we have

$$E[I_p^2, I_q^2] = p^i \|f\|^2 q^i \|g\|^2 = p^i q^i \|f \otimes g\|^2 \text{ on the other hand,}$$

$$I_p(f)_q(g) = \sum_{n=0}^{p \wedge q} n^i C_p^n C_q^n I_{p+q-2n}(f \otimes g), \text{ hence}$$

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$$E \left[\left(I_p(f) I_q(g) \right)^2 \right] = \sum_{n=0}^{p \wedge q} (n! C_p^n C_q^n)^2 (p+q-2n)! \|f \widehat{\otimes}_n g\|^2 \geq (p+q)! \|f \widehat{\otimes} g\|^2$$

(dropping the terms with $n \geq 1$)

By definition

$$\begin{aligned} \|f \widehat{\otimes} g\|^2 &= \left\| \frac{1}{(p+q)!} \sum_{\sigma \in S_{p+q}} f(t_{\sigma(1)} \dots t_{\sigma(p)}) g(t_{\sigma(p+1)} \dots t_{\sigma(p+q)}) \right\|^2 \\ &= \frac{1}{((p+q)!)^2} \sum_{\sigma, \pi \in S_{p+q}} \lambda_{\sigma, \pi} \end{aligned}$$

Where s_{p+q} represent the group of permutations of order $p+q$ and

$$\lambda_{\sigma, \pi} = [0,1]^{p+q} \int f(t_{\sigma(1)} \dots t_{\sigma(p)}) g(t_{\sigma(p+1)} \dots t_{\sigma(p+q)}) \cdot f(t_{\pi(1)} \dots t_{\pi(p)}) g(t_{\pi(p+1)} \dots t_{\pi(p+q)}) dt_1 \dots dt_{p+q}$$

Without loss of generality, we may assume that $p \leq q$. Suppose now that $(\sigma(1), \dots, \sigma(p))$ and $(\pi(1), \dots, \pi(p))$ has $r \geq 0$ elements in common, by applying the block (Kallenberg, 1991) notation, we have

$$\begin{aligned} (t_{\sigma(1)}, \dots, t_{\sigma(p)}) &= (A_r, \bar{A}) \\ (t_{\sigma(p+1)}, \dots, t_{\sigma(p+q)}) &= B \\ (t_{\pi(1)}, \dots, t_{\pi(p)}) &= (A_r, \bar{C}) \end{aligned}$$

$(t_{\pi(p+1)}, \dots, t_{\pi(p+q)}) = D$ where A_r is the sub block containing elements common to $(t_{\pi(1)}, \dots, t_{\pi(p)})$ and $(t_{\sigma(1)}, \dots, t_{\sigma(p)})$.

Then we have

$$\lambda_{\sigma, \pi} = [0,1]^{p+q} \int f(A_r, \bar{A}) g(B) \cdot f(A_r, \bar{C}) g(D) dt_1, \dots, dt_{p+q}$$

Note that $A_r \cup \bar{A} \cup B = A_r \cup \bar{C} \cup D = \{t_1, \dots, t_{p+q}\}$,
 $\bar{A} \cap \bar{C} = \emptyset$

Hence we have

$\bar{A} \cup B = \bar{C} \cup D$. Since $\bar{A} \cap \bar{C} = \emptyset$, we also have $\bar{C} \subset B$ and $\bar{A} \subset D$

The fact that $(\bar{A}, B)$ and $(\bar{C}, D)$ are the partitions of the same set, we have

$$D \setminus \bar{A} = B \setminus \bar{C}$$

Hence we can write

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_{\sigma, \pi} &= [0,1]^{p+q} \int f(A_r, \bar{A}) g(\bar{C}, B \setminus \bar{C}) \cdot f(A_r, \bar{C}) g(\bar{A}, D \setminus \bar{A}) dt_1, \dots, dt_{p+q} \\ &= [0,1]^{p+q} \int f(A_r, \bar{A}) g(\bar{C}, B \setminus \bar{C}) \cdot f(A_r, \bar{C}) g(\bar{A}, B \setminus \bar{C}) dA_r d\bar{A} d\bar{C} d(B \setminus \bar{C}) \\ &= [0,1]^{p+q} \int (f \otimes_{p-r} g)(A_r, B \setminus \bar{C}) (f \otimes_{p-r} g)(A_r, B \setminus \bar{C}) dA_r d(B \setminus \bar{C}) \\ &= \left\| f \otimes_{p-r} g \right\|_{\rho[0,1]^{p-q+2r}}^2 \end{aligned}$$

Where we have used the relation $D \setminus \bar{A} = B \setminus \bar{C}$ in the second line of the above equalities. Note that for $r = p$, we have $\lambda_{\sigma,\pi} = \|f \otimes g\|_{L^2}^2$

Hence

$$E[I_p^2(f)I_q^2(g)] = p^1 \|f\|^2 \cdot q^1 \|g\|^2 \geq (p + q)^1 \left[\frac{1}{((p+q)!)^2} [\sum_{\sigma,\pi} \lambda_{\sigma,\pi}(r = p) + \sum_{\sigma,\pi} \lambda_{\sigma,\pi}(r \neq p)] \right]$$

The number of $\lambda_{\sigma,\pi}$ with $(r = p)$ is exactly $\binom{p+q}{p} (pq^2)(q^1)^2$

Hence

$$p^1 q^1 \|f\|^2 \|g\|^2 \geq p^1 q^1 \|f \otimes g\|^2 + \sum_{r=0}^{p-1} c_r \|f \otimes_{p-r} g\|_{L^2([0,1]^{q-p+2r})}^2 \text{ with } c_r \geq 0$$

For this relation to hold, $\|f \otimes_{p-r} g\| = 0, r = 0, \dots, p-1$ in particular for $r = p-1$, we have $\|f \otimes_1 g\| = 0$

($\Leftarrow$): from proposition 3.1 below, we see that it is sufficient to prove

$$\left((1 + L)^{-1} e^{i\alpha F \nabla} I_q(g) \right) = 0 \text{ a.s with } F = I_p(f), \text{ under the hypothesis } f \otimes_1 g = 0 \text{ a.s}$$

Let

$$e^{i\alpha I_p(f)} = \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} I_r(h_r), \text{ then}$$

$$\begin{aligned} e^{i\alpha I_p(f)} \nabla I_p(f) &= p \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} I_r(h_r) \cdot I_{p-1}(f) \\ &= p \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \sum_{s=0}^{r \wedge (p-1)} \alpha_{p,r,s} I_{p-1+r-2s}(h_r \otimes_s f) \end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$(1 + L)^{-1} e^{i\alpha F} \nabla F = p \sum_r \sum_{s=0}^{r \wedge (p-1)} (1 + p + r - 1 - 2s)^{-1} I_{p-1+r-2s}(h_r \otimes_p f)$$

By taking scalar product with $\nabla I_q(g)$, we will have terms of this type;

$$\begin{aligned} &\left(I_{p-1+r-2s}(h_r \otimes f), I_{q-1}(g) \right)_H \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} I_{p-1+r-2s} \left(h_r \otimes_s f(e_i) I_{q-1}(g(e_i)) \right) \end{aligned}$$

By multiplication formula, we have

$$\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \int (h_r \otimes_s f(e_i))(t_1, \dots, t_{p+r-2s-1}) g(e_i)(t_1, \dots, t_{q-1}) dt_1 dt_2 \dots$$

$$\iint_{\theta=0}^1 (h_r \otimes_s f(\theta))(t_1, \dots, t_{p+r-2s-1})g(\theta, t_1, \dots, t_{q-1})d\theta dt_1, \dots$$

From the hypothesis,

$$\int_0^1 f(\theta, t_1, \dots)g(\theta, s_1, \dots)d\theta = 0$$

Hence the Fubini theorem complete the proof (Usunel and Zakai, 1992)

Remark :

In the proof of the necessity, we have used only the fact that $I_p(f)^2$ and $I_q(g)^2$ are independent. Hence as a by-product we obtain only the fact that I_p and I_q are independent if and only if their (Usunel and Zakai, 1992) are independent.

Log-Sobolev inequality and exponential integrability

There exist a closed relationship between the probability measures satisfying the log-sobolev inequality and the exponential integrability of the random variables having essentially bounded sobolev derivatives. We shall explain this in the frame of Wiener space (Stock and Varadhan, 1979; Kallenberg, 1991).

Let $\mathbb{p}$ be a probability measures on $(W, B(W))$ such that the operator ∇ is a closable operator on $L^2(\mathbb{p})$.

Assuming

$E_{\mathbb{p}}[\mathcal{A}_{\mathbb{p}}(f^2)] \leq TE_{\mathbb{p}} \left[|\nabla f|^2_{\mathcal{A}} \right]$ is for any cylindrical $f: W \rightarrow \mathfrak{R}$ where $\mathcal{A}_{\mathbb{p}}(f^2) = f^2(\log f^2 - \log E_{\mathbb{p}}[f^2])$ since ∇ is a closable operator, of course this inequality extends immediately to the extended L^2 -domain of it.

Lemma 3.1

Assume that f is in the extended L^2 -domain of ∇ such that $|\nabla f|_{\mathcal{A}}$ is $\mathbb{p}$ - essentially bounded by one.

Then

$$E_{\mathbb{p}}[e^{gf}] \leq \exp \left\{ gE_{\mathbb{p}}[f] + \frac{rg^2}{4} \right\} \tag{3.1}$$

For any $g \in \mathfrak{R}$

Proof :

Let $f_n = \min(|f|, n)$, then that $|\nabla f_n|_{\mathcal{A}} \leq |\nabla f|_{\mathcal{A}}$ $\mathbb{p}$ - almost surely.

Let $g \in \mathfrak{R}$ and define s_n as to be $e^{\frac{gf_n}{2}}$ also let $\theta(g)$ be the function $E[e^{gf_n}]$. Hence from the above inequality

$$g\theta'(g) - \theta(g)\log\theta(g) \leq \frac{Tg^2}{4}\theta(g) \quad (3.2)$$

If $\beta(g) = \frac{1}{g}\log\theta(g)$, then $\lim_{g \rightarrow 0} \beta(g) = E|f_n|$, and (3.2) implies $\beta'(g) \leq \frac{T}{4}$

Hence we have

$$\beta(g) \leq E_p[f_n] + \frac{Tg}{4},$$

Therefore

$$\theta(g) \leq \exp\left(gE_p[f_n] + \frac{Tg^2}{4}\right) \quad (3.3)$$

It follow from the monotone convergence theorem that $E[e^{gf}] < \infty$, for any $g \in \mathfrak{R}$. Hence the function $\theta(g) = E[e^{gf}]$ satisfies also the inequality (3.2) which implies the inequality (3.1).

Now using (3.1) and an auxillary Gaussian random variable as we can show easily:
Proposition 3.1

Assume that $f \in L^p(\mathfrak{p})$ has $\mathfrak{p}$ -essentially bounded sobolev derivative and that this bound is equal to one. Then we have for any $\varepsilon > 0$

$$E_p[e^{\varepsilon f^2}] \leq \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\varepsilon T}} \exp\left(\frac{2\varepsilon E_p[f]^2}{1-\varepsilon T}\right) \text{ provided } \varepsilon T < 1$$

An interpolation inequality.

Another useful inequality for the Wiener functional is the interpolation inequality which help to control the L^p - norm of ∇f with the help of the L^p - norm of $\mathcal{F}$ and $\nabla^2 \mathcal{F}$.

Theorem 3.1

For any $p > 1$, there exist a constant k_p , such that for any $\mathcal{F} \in \mathfrak{D}_{p,2}$ one has

$$\|\nabla \mathcal{F}\|_p^2 \leq k_p \left[\|\mathcal{F}\|_p + \|\mathcal{F}\|_p^{\frac{1}{2}} \|\nabla^2 \mathcal{F}\|_p^{\frac{1}{2}} \right]$$

The prove of theorem 3.1 will depend largely on the proof of the following theorem;

Theorem 3.2

For any $p > 1$, we have

$$\|(I + L)^{\frac{1}{2}} \mathcal{F}\|_p \leq \frac{4}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)} \|\mathcal{F}\|_p^{\frac{1}{2}} \|(I + L) \mathcal{F}\|_p^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

Proof :

Let $\mathcal{M}$ be the functional $(I + L)\mathcal{F}$, then we have $\mathcal{F} = (I + L)^{-1}\mathcal{M}$. Therefore it suffices to show that

$$\|(I + L)^{-\frac{1}{2}}\mathcal{M}\|_p \leq \frac{4}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)} \|\mathcal{M}\|_p^{\frac{1}{2}} \|(I + L)^{-1}\mathcal{M}\|_p^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

We have

$$(I + L)^{-\frac{1}{2}}\mathcal{M} = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)} \left[\int_0^\infty g^{-\frac{1}{2}e^{-g}} p_g \mathcal{M} dg \right],$$

Where p_g denotes the semi-group of Ornstein-Uhlenbeck for any $a > 0$, we can write

$$(I + L)^{-\frac{1}{2}}\mathcal{M} = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)} \left[\int_0^a g^{-\frac{1}{2}e^{-g}} p_g \mathcal{M} dg + \int_a^\infty g^{-\frac{1}{2}e^{-g}} p_g \mathcal{M} dg \right]$$

Let the two terms at the right hand side of the above inequality be represented by I_a and II_a respectively.

$$\|(I + L)^{-\frac{1}{2}}\mathcal{M}\|_p \leq \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)} [\|I_a\|_p + \|II_a\|_p].$$

The first term at right hand side can be upper bounded as

$$\|I_a\|_p \leq \int_0^a g^{-\frac{1}{2}} \|\mathcal{M}\|_p dg = \sqrt[2]{a} \|\mathcal{M}\|_p$$

Let $\mathcal{M} = (I + L)^{-1}\mathcal{M}$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \int_a^\infty g^{-\frac{1}{2}e^{-g}} p_g \mathcal{M} dg &= \int_a^\infty g^{-\frac{1}{2}e^{-g}} p_g (I + L)(I + L)^{-1}\mathcal{M} dg \\ &= \int_a^\infty g^{-\frac{1}{2}e^{-g}} p_g (I + L)S dg \\ &= \int_a^\infty g^{-\frac{1}{2}} \frac{d}{dg} (e^{-g} p_g) dg \\ &= -a^{-\frac{1}{2}} e^{-a} p_a g + \frac{1}{2} \int_a^\infty g^{-\frac{3}{2}e^{-g}} p_g S dg \end{aligned}$$

Where the third equality follows from the integration by part formula. Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \|II_a\|_p &\leq a^{-\frac{1}{2}} \|e^{-a} p_a g\|_p + \frac{1}{2} \int_a^\infty g^{-\frac{3}{2}} \|e^{-g} p_g S\|_p dg \\ &\leq a^{-\frac{1}{2}} \|S\|_p + \frac{1}{2} \int_a^\infty g^{-\frac{3}{2}} \|S\|_p dg \\ &= 2a^{-\frac{1}{2}} \|S\|_p \end{aligned}$$

$$= 2a^{-\frac{1}{2}}\|(I + L)^{-1}\mathcal{M}\|_p$$

Finally we have

$$\|(I + L)^{-1}\mathcal{M}\|_p \leq \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\Gamma(\frac{1}{2})} \left[a^{-\frac{1}{2}}\|\mathcal{M}\|_p + a^{-\frac{1}{2}}\|(I + L)^{-1}\mathcal{M}\|_p \right]$$

This expression (Deereusefond and Ustunel, 1998) minimum when we take

$$a = \frac{\|(I + L)^{-1}\mathcal{M}\|_p}{\|\mathcal{M}\|_p}$$

Exponential Integrability of the square of the Wiener functional

We shall begin by stating two lemmas which are of some interest particularly in this research work.

Lemma 4.1

Let $\phi \in L^p(\mu), p > 1$, then, for any $h \in H, t > 0$ we have

$$\nabla_h P_t \phi(x) = \frac{e^{-t}}{\sqrt{1 - e^{-2t}}} \int_w \phi \left(e^{-t}x + \sqrt{1 - e^{-2t}}y \right) \delta h(y) \mu(dy)$$

Almost surely, where $\nabla_h P_t \phi$ represents $(\nabla P_t \phi, h)H$.

Proof:

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_h P_t \phi(x) &= \frac{d}{d\lambda} \Big|_{\lambda=0} \int_w \phi \left(e^{-t}(x + \lambda h) + \sqrt{1 - e^{-2t}}y \right) \mu(dy) \\ &= \frac{d}{d\lambda} \Big|_{\lambda=0} \int_w \phi \left(e^{-t}x + \sqrt{1 - e^{-2t}} \left(y + \frac{\lambda e^{-t}}{\sqrt{1 - e^{-2t}}} h \right) \right) \mu(dy) \\ &= \frac{d}{d\lambda} \Big|_{\lambda=0} \int_w \phi \left(e^{-t}x + \sqrt{1 - e^{-2t}}y \right) \varepsilon \left(\frac{\lambda e^{-t}}{\sqrt{1 - e^{-2t}}} \delta h \right) (y) \mu(dy) \\ &= \int_w \phi \left(e^{-t}x + \sqrt{1 - e^{-2t}}y \right) \frac{\lambda e^{-t}}{\sqrt{1 - e^{-2t}}} \delta h(y) \mu(dy), \end{aligned}$$

Where $\varepsilon(\delta h)$ denotes $\exp \left(\delta h - \frac{1}{2|h|_H^2} \right)$.

Lemma 4.2

Let $\xi \in L^p(\mu, H), p > 1$ and for $(x, y) \in W \times W, t \geq 0$,

Define

$$R_t(x, y) = e^{-t}x + (1 - e^{-2t})^{\frac{1}{2}}y$$

And

$$S_t(x, y) = (1 - e^{-2t})^{1/2}x - e^{-t}y.$$

Then $S_t(x, y)$ and $R_t(x, y)$ are independent, identically distributed Gaussian random variables on $W \times W, \mu(dx) \times \mu(dy)$. Moreover the following identity holds true (Stock and Varadhan, 1979; Usunel and Zakai, 1992).

$$P_t \delta \xi(x) = \frac{e^{-t}}{\sqrt{1 - e^{-2t}}} \int_w I_1 \left(\xi(R_t(x, y)) \right) (S_t(x, y)) \mu(dy),$$

Where

$$I_1 \left(\xi(R_t(x, y)) \right) (S_t(x, y))$$

Denotes the first order Wiener integral of $\xi(R_t(x, y))$ with respect to the independent path $S_t(x, y)$ under the product measure $\mu(dx) \times \mu(dy)$. Proof omitted.

In order to control the moment like $E \left[\exp \left\{ \|\nabla \eta\|_2^2 \right\} \right]$, where η is an H -valued random variable and $\|\cdot\|_2$ denotes the Hilbert-Schmidt norm, we require the following proposition which is stated without proof (Chang *et al.*, 2009; Dereusefond *et al.*, 1993).

Proposition 4.1

Suppose that $\beta > 1/2$ and that $\eta \in D_{2,2\beta}(H)$ then we have

$$E \left[\exp \left\{ \|\nabla \eta\|_2^2 \right\} \right] \leq E \left[\exp \left\{ (I + \mathcal{L})^\beta \eta \right\}_H^2 \right].$$

For any

$$c \geq c_0 = \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_{R_+} \tau^{\beta-1} e^{-2t} (1 - e^{-2t})^{-\frac{1}{2}} dt \right]^2.$$

In particular, for $\beta = 1$ we have $c \geq 1/4$

Summary and Conclusion

This paper has examined the application of Stochastic iterated integral to moment inequalities for Wiener Functionals by considering two results as stated in section 1, the combination of these results engender some interesting concepts which can be exploited for further research.

In actual fact, the exponential integrability of the square of the Wiener functional has one of its most prominent applications in the analysis of non-linear Gaussian functional. Also applying the interpolation inequality, we have been able to depict that the Sobolev norm of the first order can be upper bounded by the product of the second order and of the zero-th order Sobolev norm. however this paper have only examined two moment inequalities, log-Sobolev and interpolation inequalities from which we established the fact that the log-Sobolev inequality implies the exponential integrability of the square of the wiener functional and also a closed relationship between the probability measures satisfying the log-sobolev inequality and the exponential integrability of the random variables.

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